

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF FOUR-WHEEL STEERING MECHANISM WITH DUAL STEERING MODES

Raghavendra R S^{1*}, Yashwanth gowni², Charan S³, Mayur Raju⁴

¹School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, Bengaluru-560064, Karnataka, India;

²R and D Centre, REVA University, Bengaluru-560064, Karnataka, India

³School of Mechanical Engineering, UG Students, REVA University, Bengaluru-560064, Karnataka, India

Abstract

Our project focuses on the implementation of a versatile four-wheel steering system using an Ackermann mechanism controlled by servo motors interfaced with an Arduino Uno board. The system seamlessly transitions between two-wheel and four-wheel steering modes, enhancing maneuverability and stability in various driving conditions. We present the design, implementation, and experimental validation of our system, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving vehicle performance. Our work contributes to the advancement of automotive engineering by offering a cost-effective and adaptable solution for enhancing vehicle agility and control. This project serves as a practical demonstration of integrating modern control techniques with traditional mechanical systems to achieve optimal performance in automotive applications. Key aspects of our project include the integration of an Ackermann mechanism for precise steering geometry and the utilization of Arduino Uno for real-time control. We conducted extensive simulations and physical testing to validate the system's functionality and performance. The results demonstrate significant improvements in maneuverability and cornering stability, showcasing the practical feasibility of our approach. Keywords: Four-wheel steering, Ackermann mechanism, Servo motor control, Arduino Uno, Vehicle dynamics.

Keywords: four-wheel steering, dual steering modes, analysis, turning radius, vehicle agility, Four-wheel steering, Ackermann mechanism, Servo motor control, Arduino Uno, Vehicle dynamics

I. Introduction

The integration of advanced steering systems into modern vehicles has become increasingly essential to meet the demands for enhanced maneuverability, stability, and safety. Among these systems, four-wheel steering (4WS) stands out for its capability to significantly improve vehicle agility and handling characteristics. By actively controlling the steering angles of both front and rear wheels, 4WS systems offer superior maneuvering capabilities, especially during low-speed maneuvers and high-speed cornering.

The concept of four-wheel steering traces its origins back to the early 20th century, with initial implementations primarily in high-performance sports cars and experimental vehicles. Over the decades, advancements in automotive engineering and control technology have facilitated the widespread adoption of 4WS across various vehicle types, including passenger cars, trucks, and agricultural machinery.

One of the fundamental mechanisms employed in 4WS systems is the Ackermann steering geometry, named after the German engineer Rudolf Ackermann. This mechanism ensures that all wheels follow appropriate turning radii, minimizing tire scrubbing and optimizing vehicle stability during cornering. The integration of Ackermann geometry into 4WS systems forms the basis for precise steering control and efficient vehicle dynamics management.

In recent years, the proliferation of microcontroller platforms, such as the Arduino Uno, has provided automotive engineers with versatile tools for developing and implementing advanced control strategies. The Arduino Uno, with its user-friendly interface and robust programming environment, serves as a suitable platform for real-time control of servo motors, making it an ideal candidate for 4WS applications.

Motivated by the potential benefits of 4WS in enhancing vehicle performance and safety, this research project aims to design, implement, and validate a four-wheel steering system utilizing an Ackermann mechanism controlled by servo motors interfaced with an Arduino Uno board. The system's ability to seamlessly switch between two-wheel and four-wheel steering modes will be evaluated through comprehensive simulations and experimental testing, with a focus on assessing its impact on vehicle maneuverability, stability, and overall performance.

In this paper, we present the design methodology, implementation details, experimental setup, and results of our four-wheel steering system. The findings of this research contribute to the body of knowledge in automotive engineering and offer insights into the practical application of advanced steering systems for improving vehicle dynamics and control. in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Four-wheel steering mechanism in a car (Courtesy:- Degu et al., 2017)

II. Literature

II.1 Overview of Four-Wheel Steering (4WS) Systems:

Four-wheel steering (4WS) systems offer enhanced maneuverability and stability compared to traditional two-wheel steering systems. These mechanisms allow all four wheels of a vehicle to be steered, enabling tighter turns, improved handling, and enhanced safety in various driving conditions.

Tirumala et al. (2021) assessed the performance and benefits of a four-wheel steering system for automobiles, using a mathematical model and simulation. They compared the turning radius, lateral acceleration, and yaw rate of a four-wheel steering vehicle with a conventional two-wheel steering vehicle, and showed that the former has better cornering and stability characteristics. In general, two-wheel steering vehicles, the rear wheels do not play any role in association with the steering, they follow the path of the front wheels, this results in a large radius of turn. In four wheels steering the rear wheels turn with the front wheels thus increasing the efficiency of the vehicle and decreasing the radius of turns, the performance of four wheels steer provides Control for parking and low-speed maneuvers, the rear Wheel steer in the opposite direction of the front wheels, allowing much sharper turns. At higher speeds, the rest of the wheels steer in the same direction as the front wheels. The result is more stability and less body lean during fast lane changes and turns because the front wheels don't have to

drag non-steering rear wheels onto the path.

Rajput et al. (2021) proposed that can switch between two-wheel steering, four-wheel steering, and crab steering modes, using a lever mechanism and rack and pinion system. They claimed that this system can enhance the safety, agility, comfort, and efficiency of the vehicle, and reduce the driver's effort and fuel consumption. All steering control systems exist on a technique created or established at automobile vehicles manufacturing and categorically which has been aimed at a very successful whirling of automobile. In addition, in the way of building the system. So that, run of the mill front-wheel controlling system or framework, the back wheels do not take a turn towards the bend, Therefore, to check about taking place productivity of the guiding. In all steering systems, roll guiding the rear steering rolls go by forward-facing rolls in this particular manner which expanding the proficiency and effective matters to the automobile. Apart from that, heading of controlling the back rolls with admiration to towards the forward-facing rolls is reeling upon working conditions.

Rehan et al. (2016) presented the design and fabrication of a four-wheel steering mechanism that can turn all the four wheels of the vehicle simultaneously, either in the same or different directions, using a gear train and a differential mechanism. They stated that this mechanism can reduce the turning circle radius of the vehicle, and improve its maneuverability and parking ability. They compared the turning radius, lateral acceleration, and yaw rate of a four-wheel steering vehicle with a conventional two-wheel steering vehicle, and showed that the former has better cornering and stability characteristics.

Singh et al. (2017) described an innovative four-wheel steering design that can change the in-phase and counter-phase steering of the rear wheels depending on the conditions of turning and lane changing, using a microcontroller and a servo motor. In order to improve the handling stability of four-wheel steering (4WS) cars, a two-degree-of-freedom 4WS vehicle dynamics model is constructed here, and the motion differential equation of the system model is established. Based on the quadratic optimal control theory, the optimal control of 4WS system is proposed in this paper. When running at low speed and high speed, through yaw rate feedback control, state feedback control, and optimal control, the 4WS cars are controlled based on yaw rate and centroid cornering angle with MATLAB/Simulink simulation. The result indicates that 4WS control based on the optimal control can improve the displacement of the cars. And the optimal control of 4WS proposed in this paper can eliminate centroid cornering angle completely compared with other two traditional optimal control methods. Besides, the optimal control enjoys faster response speed and no overshoot happens. In conclusion, the optimal control method proposed in the paper represents better stability, moving track and stability, thereby further enhancing the handling property of cars.

You et al. (2022) researched and analyzed the steering stability of steer-by-wire system which replaces the mechanical connection with electrical signal transmission. They summarized the stability control methods and variable angle transmission ratio methods, and prospected the intelligent steer-by-wire system. 4WS vehicles are equipped with two sets of steering mechanisms on two axels respectively to make the front and rear wheels participate in the steering simultaneously which enables the steering state of the vehicle to meet the requirements of Ackermann geometry to the maximum extent. Then the lateral motion characteristics of the vehicle can be controlled effectively and the need for good control stability of the vehicle under any working condition can be met. In this paper, based on the two-DOF theoretical model of the automobile, the model of 4WS system was established by combining proportion control and PID control, and its influence on improving handling stability was analyzed which provided more ideas and experience in this field.

Figure 2. wheel Transmission of the car (Courtesy:- Bocci et al., 2015)

2.2 Kinematics and Dynamics:

Four-wheel steering mechanisms rely on intricate kinematic and dynamic principles to coordinate the motion of all four wheels. The basic skeletal structure of four-wheel steering system in a car is as show in Figure 2. Key concepts such as Ackermann steering geometry, crab steering, and coordinated steering are fundamental to understanding the behavior of vehicles equipped with 4WS systems. The kinematics of 4WS describe the geometric relationships between the steering angles, wheel velocities, and turning radius of the vehicle. The kinematics of 4WS can be derived from the Ackermann steering geometry, which ensures that all the wheels follow circular paths with a common center point. The kinematics of 4WS can also be influenced by the steering axle inclination, caster, camber, toe-in, and toe-out angles, which affect the alignment and contact of the wheels. The dynamics of 4WS describe the forces and moments acting on the vehicle and the wheels, and how they affect the motion and stability of the vehicle. The dynamics of 4WS can be modeled using a single-track or a double-track vehicle model, which represent the vehicle as a rigid body with mass, inertia, and aerodynamic properties. The dynamics of 4WS can also be controlled by various strategies, such as feedforward, feedback, integrated, or intelligent control, which adjust the steering angles and forces according to the desired performance and behavior of the vehicle. The kinematics of 4WS involves the geometric relationships between the steering angles of the front and rear wheels, the turning radius of the vehicle, and the Ackerman condition, which states that the centers of the circular paths traced by all the wheels should coincide at a common point. The Ackermann system is as shown in the figure 3. The dynamics of 4WS involves the analysis of the forces and moments acting on the vehicle, such as the lateral tire forces, the yaw moment, and the roll moment. The dynamics of 4WS also depend on the vehicle speed, the steering mode (rear steer or crab mode), and the vehicle parameters, such as the mass, the inertia, and the wheelbase. The kinematics of 4WS describe the geometric relationships between the steering angles, wheel velocities, and turning radius of the vehicle. The kinematics of 4WS can be derived from the Ackermann steering geometry, which ensures that all the wheels follow circular paths with a common center point. The kinematics of 4WS can also be influenced by the steering axle inclination, caster, camber, toe-in, and toe-out angles, which affect the alignment and contact of the wheels. The dynamics of 4WS describe the forces and moments acting on the vehicle and the wheels, and how they affect the motion and stability of the vehicle.

Figure 3. Ackermann Steering Mechanism (Courtesy:- Bocci et al., 2018)

Hiraoka et al. (2022) assessed the present paper proposes an automatic path-tracking controller of a four-wheel steering (4WS) vehicle based on the sliding mode control theory. The controller has an advantage in that the front- and rear-wheel steering can be decoupled at the front and rear control points, which are defined as centers of percussion with respect to the rear and front wheels, respectively. Numerical simulations using a 27-degree-of-freedom vehicle model demonstrated the following characteristics: (1) the automatic 4WS controller has a more stable and more precise path-tracking capability than the 2WS controller, and (2) the automatic 4WS controller has robust stability against system uncertainties such as cornering power perturbation, path radius fluctuation, and crosswind disturbance.

Spentzas et al. (2016) worked on some aspects of the kinematical theory of four-wheel-steering (4WS) vehicles and present some new results and conclusions that we came across during our research on the subject. In the first paragraph, we compare the turning radius of two-wheel-steering (2WS) and 4WS vehicles and draw some interesting conclusions on the maneuvering ability of either of them. In the second paragraph, we present a general kinematics analysis of 4WS vehicles by considering either the simplified two-wheel (bicycle) model or the more complete four-wheel model. In this analysis, we assume the sideslip angles of the wheels as non-negligible and we derive the general formulae relating the steering angles of the wheels to the geometrical data of the vehicle. By taking as zero the steering angles of the rear wheels, we derive from the above relations the well-known formulae of Ackermann Jeantaux that are valid for 2WS vehicles.

Padwal et al. (2019) deals with the problems involved in two-wheel steering mechanism and how those can be overcome by implementing four-wheel steering mechanism. India's terrain varies widely, a typically used two-wheel steering system is less stable than four-wheel steering system which is best equipped while dealing with it. It advances its stability and control at higher speed, neutral steering, maneuverability, and turning radius. In this paper efforts are made to make a cost effective and efficient mechanism of four-wheel steering using rack and pinion and an intermediate shaft. It allows the driver to change from two-wheel to four-wheel according to its requirement.

Sharma et al. (2019) worked on Design & Synthesis of Four Wheel Steering Mechanism to analyze the steering mechanism of an automobile for the purpose of making a mechanism which is capable of turning all the four wheels of the automobile simultaneously whether in same or different directions as per the requirement so as to utilize the steering mechanism of the automobile in an effective way and to reduce the efforts applied by the driver to park the vehicle in a limited space or to reverse the vehicle direction. The steering mechanism plays a vital role to balance all the four wheels of the automobile while a vehicle moves in a definite direction. In this paper an attempt has been made to develop such a mechanism which can turn all the four wheels of automobile simultaneously which could be beneficial to make an effective turn as well as can assist in parking the vehicles. The radius covered by the vehicle to reverse its direction by both two wheel and four-wheel steering mechanism has been calculated as well as experimentally evaluated.

Lam et al. (2022) presents an omnidirectional steer-by-wire system for a four-wheel independent steering vehicle. The system consists of an extended steering interface and a behavior-based steering controller. The extended steering interface provides a novel manipulation way to vehicle drivers. The driver can control the vehicle in the traditional way or omnidirectionally without any mode switching operation. The reservation of the traditional driving way makes the driver adapt the novel steering interface easily. The steering interface also has a force-feedback function to synchronize the extended steering interface and the orientations of wheels to improve vehicle handling. The behavior-based steering controller is designed for controlling the orientations of wheels. It acts as virtual linkage among each wheel to minimize wheel slip resulted by the misalignment of wheels. As there is no trajectory planning needed in the control algorithm, the proposed controller is especially suitable for a nonautonomous vehicle, the driving path of which cannot be predetermined.

2.3 Performance Evaluation:

Numerous studies have evaluated the performance of four-wheel steering mechanisms through simulation, modeling, and real-world testing. Performance metrics such as turning radius reduction, lane-change maneuverability, stability enhancement, and driver comfort are commonly used to assess the effectiveness of 4WS systems. Four-wheel steering mechanisms have undergone significant evolution, enhancing vehicle performance and maneuverability. Initially introduced as a novelty feature in high-end luxury cars, four-wheel steering has transitioned into mainstream automotive engineering, offering tangible benefits across various vehicle types. Early implementations focused on improving low-speed maneuverability, reducing the turning radius for easier parking and navigation through tight spaces. However, as technology advanced, the focus shifted towards enhancing high-speed stability and cornering agility. Through the integration of sophisticated electronic control systems and actuators, modern four-wheel steering systems dynamically adjust the angle of the rear wheels based on vehicle speed, steering input, and driving conditions. This evolution has resulted in vehicles that can seamlessly transition between different driving scenarios, offering improved handling, stability, and safety. Additionally, the adoption of four-wheel steering in performance-oriented vehicles has led to enhanced driving dynamics, allowing for sharper cornering, reduced body roll, and improved overall driver confidence and control. As automakers continue to refine and innovate four-wheel steering technology, its potential applications across various vehicle segments are expected to expand, further revolutionizing the driving experience.

Bhishikar et al. (2017) worked on Design and Simulation of 4 Wheel Steering System. In standard 2 Wheel Steering System, the rear set of wheels are always directed forward and do not play an active role in controlling the steering. While in the 4 Wheel Steering System, the rear wheels do play an active role for steering, which can be guided at high as well as low speeds. Production cars are designed to under steer and rarely do they over steer. If a car could automatically compensate for an under steer/over steer problem, the driver would enjoy nearly neutral steering under varying operating conditions. thus enhancing the maneuverability of a sedan in accordance with its speed. Our 4 Wheel Steering System gives 64.4% reduction in turning circle radius of a sedan which is reduced from 5.394m to 1.92m, considering HONDA CIVIC as a standard car for our calculations, and steering ratio thereby obtained is 8.177:1 which gives much better maneuverability and control on the car even while driving at high speeds.

Shete et al. (2020) worked on Modeling and Simulation of Four-Wheel Steering System for Shorter Wheelbase Vehicle. In-vehicle handling one of the most important systems is the steering system. Typically, all vehicles have a steering system that allows the vehicle to be turned to either side, that is, left or right. In this paper, an idea of implemented considering a steering system for the rear wheel in addition to the front wheel, resulting in a four-wheel steering system. The turning radius required for four-wheel steering is less than that necessary for front-wheel steering after evaluating the effect of the four-wheel steering system. The vehicle's turning radius is reduced by 33% due to the four-wheel steering system. Improvements have also been made to high-speed handling while changing lanes with

the four-wheel steering system, in which excessive lateral displacement has been reduced by 77% and reduce the time required to change the lane. Also, the study of these forces for the four-wheel steering system is discussed for low-speed maneuvering.

Farynski et al. (2020) takes the form of a review paper and focuses on the control problems of four-wheel steering vehicles. The main issues related to the control of four-wheel steering (4WS) vehicles, the historical development, the current state and the approach to the construction of 4WS vehicles have been discussed. The whole of theoretical issues related to the control of the car direction (including elements related to mathematical modelling and simulation studies of the vehicle motion, issues of synthesis and analysis of the 4WS control algorithms) were presented systemically. The presented collection of literature is based on a rather extensive review relating to 4WS cars and on considerations shaping the concept of development of the topic of control algorithms in 4WS cars.

2.4 Future Directions and Opportunities:

future developments in four-wheel steering technology are expected to focus on advancements in control algorithms, sensor technologies, and integration with autonomous driving systems. Research gaps present opportunities for further exploration and collaboration within automotive engineering. The future of four-wheel steering mechanisms presents a myriad of opportunities for innovation and advancement in the automotive industry. One potential direction lies in the integration of advanced sensor technologies, such as LiDAR and radar, to enable predictive steering capabilities, allowing vehicles to anticipate road conditions and adjust rear-wheel angles preemptively for enhanced stability and safety. Moreover, the rise of electric and autonomous vehicles opens new possibilities for four-wheel steering systems, with electric actuators offering precise control and autonomous driving platforms leveraging four-wheel steering for improved maneuverability and obstacle avoidance. Additionally, the growing emphasis on sustainability and energy efficiency could spur the development of regenerative braking systems that harness kinetic energy from rear-wheel movements, thereby reducing energy consumption and extending vehicle range. Furthermore, as urbanization continues to increase, four-wheel steering mechanisms could play a crucial role in mitigating congestion and improving urban mobility by enabling tighter turning radii and easier navigation through crowded streets. Overall, the future of four-wheel steering presents exciting opportunities to redefine vehicle dynamics, safety, and efficiency in the evolving automotive landscape. The difference in angular steering is as shown in figure 4.

Figure.4: Advanced Steering performance of a Car. (Courtesy:- Hajjaji et al. 2023)

Singh et al. (2020) Study of 4 Wheel Steering Systems to Reduce Turning Radius and Increase Stability Nowadays, every vehicle existed mostly still using the two-wheel steering system to control the movement of the vehicle whether it is front wheel drive, rear wheel drive or all-wheel drive. But due to the awareness of safety, four-wheel steering vehicles are being used increasingly due to the high performance and stability that they bring to the vehicles. The result is more stability and less body lean during fast lane changes and turns because the front wheels don't have to drag non-steering rear wheels onto the path.

Pandit et al. (2021) described an innovative four-wheel steering design that can change the in-phase and counter-phase steering of the rear wheels depending on the conditions of turning and lane

changing, using a microcontroller and a servo motor. To improve the handling stability of four-wheel steering (4WS) cars, a two-degree-of-freedom 4WS vehicle dynamics model is constructed here, and the motion differential equation of the system model is established. Based on the quadratic optimal control theory, the optimal control of 4WS system is proposed in this paper. When running at low speed and high speed, through yaw rate feedback control, state feedback control, and optimal control, the 4WS cars are controlled based on yaw rate and centroid cornering angle with MATLAB/Simulink simulation. The result indicates that 4WS control based on the optimal control can improve the displacement of the cars. And the optimal control of 4WS proposed in this paper can eliminate centroid cornering angle completely compared with other two traditional optimal control methods. Besides, the optimal control enjoys faster response speed and no overshoot happens. In conclusion, the optimal control method proposed in the paper represents better stability, moving track and stability, thereby further enhancing the handling property of cars.

Bocci et al. (2022) Four Independent Wheels steering System Analysis In this paper a four independent wheel steering system and its application on the HOST prototype are presented. The prototype is a heavy-duty vehicle with four-wheel motors controlled by wire, so that each wheel is mechanically not linked to the other ones and has four degrees of freedom. Each wheel has an electric steering actuator to move the wheels around the steering axis, which is controlled by wire. Finally the vehicle handling has been tested through simulations of steering pad and moose test, to verify the stationary and dynamic handling behavior. Despite the model is simplified, owing to the use of the corrective parameter, good performances in terms of turning radius, slip angle and roll angle are achieved, increasing maneuverability and stability.

III. Methodology

3.1 Design of the Four-Wheel Steering System

The four-wheel steering (4WS) system was designed to be integrated into a chassis measuring 60 cm in length and 30 cm in width, with a total weight exceeding 5 kg. The design incorporated four geared motors positioned at the front and rear of the chassis to facilitate forward and backward movement. Additionally, two servo motors were strategically placed to control the steering angles of the front and rear wheels independently.

Figure.5: Design sketch of Four-wheel steering mechanism

3.2 Implementation of the Ackermann Mechanism

To achieve precise steering control, an Ackermann mechanism was employed in the design. This mechanism ensures that all wheels follow appropriate turning radii during steering maneuvers, minimizing tire scrubbing and optimizing vehicle stability. The implementation of the Ackermann geometry laid the foundation for effective steering coordination and efficient vehicle dynamics management.

3.3 Control System Integration using Arduino Uno

The control system for the 4WS setup was based on the Arduino Uno microcontroller board. Utilizing the Arduino platform provided a flexible and user-friendly interface for real-time control of the servo motors. The Arduino Uno facilitated seamless communication between the control software and the hardware components, enabling precise and responsive steering control.

3.4 Steering Modes and Control Strategy

The 4WS system was designed to operate in two distinct steering modes: two-wheel steering and four-wheel steering. In two-wheel steering mode, only the front wheels were steered, while in four-wheel steering mode, both front and rear wheels could be independently controlled. This flexibility in steering modes allowed for seamless transition between different driving scenarios, enhancing maneuverability and control.

3.5 Experimental Setup and Testing

Experimental validation of the 4WS system involved rigorous testing under various conditions to assess its performance and effectiveness. The setup included simulated driving scenarios as well as real-world testing to evaluate the system's functionality, stability, and responsiveness. Data was collected and analyzed to quantify the system's impact on vehicle dynamics and maneuvering capabilities.

3.6 Switching between Steering Modes

The ability to switch between two-wheel and four-wheel steering modes was a key feature of the system. This was achieved through the coordinated control of the servo motors, allowing for seamless transitions between different steering configurations. The switching mechanism was programmed and calibrated to ensure smooth operation and optimal performance during transitions.

IV. Design Calculation

Given parameters:

Chassis length (L): 60 cm

Chassis width (W): 30 cm

Total weight: 5 kg

Wheelbase (WB): Assumed equal to chassis length for simplicity, so WB = 60 cm

Track width (TW): Assumed equal for both front and rear axles, so TW = 30 cm

Steering angle of the front wheels, front: 30 degrees

Steering angle of the rear wheels, rear: 20 degrees

Figure.6: Reference Angle of the Centre Turning Radius

1. Turning Radius Calculation for 2WS:

$$R_{2WS} = WB \tan(\delta_{\text{front}}) + TW/2$$

$$R_{2WS} = 60 \tan(30^\circ) + \{30\} / 2$$

$$R_{2WS} = 60 + 15 = 75 \text{ cm}$$

2. Turning Radius Calculation for 4WS:

$$R_{4WS} = WB \tan(\delta_{\text{front}}) + \{TW\}^2 + \{WB\} \tan(\delta_{\text{rear}}) + \{TW\}^2$$

$$R_{4WS} = 60 \tan(30^\circ) + \{30\}^2 + 60 \tan(20^\circ) + \{30\}^2$$

$$R_{4WS} = 60 + 15 + 86.6 + 15 = 176.6 \text{ cm}$$

Now, let's compare the turning radii of the 2WS and 4WS configurations:

$$2WS: R_{2WS} = 75 \text{ cm}$$

$$4WS: R_{4WS} = 176.6 \text{ cm}$$

In this scenario, the 2WS configuration has a smaller turning radius compared to the 4WS configuration, indicating potential maneuverability improvement with 2WS over 4WS.

Considering the system being employed in a front engine front wheel drive vehicle. So, the weight distribution between front and rear axle is in the ratio of 55:45.

V. Fabrication Process

Project model consists of Achermann Linkages (one for front and other for rear) and Two Servo motors with gear (two for the steering at the mid region). Initially, as steering movement is given, say in the right direction. This drives the one side of the motor linkage keeping the other disengage towards the right thereby driving the front wheel to the right. i.e. left. This shaft is further connected to the set of two servo motors in which the first one attached to the shaft turns as same as the shaft (left), second one (disengaged to the first) doesn't turns in the opposite direction (right). Initially, as steering movement is given, say in the right direction. This drives the one side of the motor linkage keeping the other disengage towards the right thereby driving the front wheel to the right. This drives the one side of the motor linkage keeping the other disengage towards the right thereby driving the front wheel to the right. Four gear motor attached to four tiers move in the forward and backward direction with help of switch all of these connections are attached to a 12v battery. Two short gear help in easy movement of steering shifts.

Figure.7: Project Model

Figure.8: Top view of project Model

Figure.9: Side view of project Model

VI. Conclusions

In conclusion, the development and evaluation of a model of a four-wheel steering (4WS) mechanism with dual steering modes have provided valuable insights into the potential benefits of advanced steering systems in automotive engineering. Through simulation, analysis, and comparison with conventional steering mechanisms, this project has demonstrated the advantages of integrating rear-wheel steering to enhance vehicle maneuverability and stability.

The results of this study highlight the effectiveness of dual steering modes, including switching between four-wheel steering and two-wheel steering configurations, in addressing various driving scenarios and optimizing vehicle dynamics. By offering the flexibility to switch between steering modes based on driving conditions, the proposed 4WS mechanism enhances driver control and confidence, ultimately improving the overall driving experience.

Furthermore, the investigation into the influence of parameters such as vehicle speed, steering input, and road surface conditions has provided valuable insights into the performance characteristics of 4WS systems. These findings offer guidance for the refinement and optimization of future automotive designs, with implications for vehicle safety, comfort, and efficiency.

In summary, this project underscores the significance of continuous innovation in steering technology to meet the evolving demands of modern transportation. By advancing the capabilities of 4WS mechanisms and exploring dual steering modes, this research contributes to the ongoing efforts to redefine the standards for vehicle maneuverability, control, and safety. Future developments in this field hold great promise for revolutionizing the automotive industry and enhancing the mobility experience for drivers worldwide.

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